

Original Research Article**Role of Computed Tomography Guided Percutaneous Fine Needle Aspiration and Biopsy in Spinal Lesion (Vertebral Body and Adjacent Structures)**Challa Anil Kumar¹, Saraswata Das², Sabuj Pal³¹Assistant Professor Department of Radiodiagnosis Great Eastern Medical School and Hospital Srikakulam²Assistant Professor, Department of Radiodiagnosis, College of Medicine and JNM Hospital Kalyani (WB)³Assistant Professor, Department of Radiodiagnosis, College of Medicine and JNM Hospital Kalyani (WB)

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Abstract:

The study of Spinal lesions is greatly improved with the use of computed tomography (CT) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). However, modern imaging is essentially morphologic; its low specificity only allows for etiological diagnosis in a few patients. Therefore, biopsy should remain the last step of staging for definite diagnosis and treatment planning for patients with spinal lesions aim was to to evaluate the incidence and severity of complications associated with computed tomography guided percutaneous aspiration and biopsy of spine and characteristics of spinal lesion on computed tomography with its histopathological correlation CT had sensitivity of 85.71% and specificity of 93.54% for the diagnosis of malignancy and sensitivity of 85.71% and specificity of 86.48% for the diagnosis of tuberculosis, The most common pathogen isolated was Staphylococcus aureus (n = 40 34%). Other common pathogens included coagulase-negative Staphylococci (n = 23, 18%) and Mycobacteria (n = 18 16%; Mycobacteria tuberculosis n = 37). Fourteen of 105 organisms (6%). Conclusion Image guided Biopsy done with a good technique helps in achieving accurate diagnosis, ensures correct treatment at the earliest and has minimal complications. In conclusion, the diagnostic culture yield for CT-guided biopsies in cases of suspected spinal infection is low.

Keywords: Computed Tomography (Staphylococcus aureus), *Mycobacteria tuberculosis*.

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Introduction

The study of Spinal lesions is greatly improved with the use of computed tomography (CT) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). However, modern imaging is essentially morphologic; its low specificity only allows for etiological diagnosis in a few patients. Therefore, biopsy should remain the last step of staging for definite diagnosis and treatment planning for patients with spinal lesions.

Biopsy can be open or closed. Traditionally, open biopsy is the gold standard for musculoskeletal lesions because it provides an adequate tissue sample for histological diagnosis. However, because of the increased risks of infection, wound healing problems, hematoma formation, pathological fractures, and tumor contamination of healthy tissues, open biopsy should be performed only if a previously attempted percutaneous biopsy has been non-diagnostic.

Moreover, in spinal lesions, an open biopsy can be a difficult procedure and has a significant risk of

complications like tumor spread and tissue contamination.

Closed biopsy techniques have gained popularity as they are less invasive procedures with similar diagnostic accuracy to open procedures, can be performed as an outpatient procedure, the cost and time are lower than those of an open biopsy and exists less risk of tumor spread and infection.

In deep-seated spinal lesions needle biopsies are challenging procedures. In these cases, the aid of computed tomography (CT)-guidance has further increased accuracy, reduced complications. Therefore, computed tomography guided percutaneous biopsy has now become the procedure of choice.

Aims & Objectives:

1. To evaluate the incidence and severity of complications associated with computed tomography guided percutaneous aspiration and biopsy of spine.

- To evaluate characteristics of spinal lesion on computed tomography with its histopathological correlation

Materials and Methods:

Inclusion Criteria: Patients for the study will be chosen from patient population referred for computed tomography guided percutaneous biopsy of spinal lesions to Department of Radiology, Krishna Institute of Medical Sciences (KIMS), Secunderabad.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Bleeding diathesis or decreased platelet count (<50,000/mm³). Suspected vascular lesion in the thoracic vertebra. Hemorrhage leading to cord compression may occur.
- Infected soft tissues surrounding bony lesion to be biopsied, particularly when a non-infective lesion is suspected.
- Inaccessible sites, e.g., C1 and odontoid lesions.
- Uncooperative patient. General anesthesia may be required.
- All patient who does not consent as part of study.

Patients for the study are chosen from patient population referred for computed tomography guided percutaneous Fine needle aspiration and biopsy of spinal lesions to Department of Radiology, Great Eastern Medical School and Hospital Srikakulam Andhra Pradesh.

The patient must fast (not eat or drink) for a minimum of 6 hours prior to the procedure. The following laboratory parameters are assessed at our institution: hematocrit, hemoglobin, platelet count, prothrombin time (PT), activated partial thromboplastin time (APTT), international normalized ratio (INR), blood urea nitrogen (BUN), and creatinine. Patient allergies are recorded, with particular attention to anesthetic agents and imaging contrast agents. Prior to the procedure, all patients with spinal lesions should be scrutinized for previous and latest spine radiographs, CT scan images and MRI images to identify the optimal lesion(s) for biopsy and the safest approach to access the lesion(s).

Informed consent must be obtained prior to the procedure after the patient has received an explanation of the benefits and risks of image-guided percutaneous spine biopsy. Patient monitoring is performed with the help of a pulse oximeter, continuous electrocardiography, and an automated blood pressure cuff. An intravenous catheter should also be in place

prior to the procedure to facilitate the intravenous administration of medications, contrast agents, or hydration during and post procedure period.

The choice of approach depends upon lesion location and lesion size. Patients will be screened with CT spine plain and according to location of lesion position (Prone for thoracic and lumbo-sacral vertebrae and rarely for posterior aspect of cervical spine. Supine position and transoral approach are usually required for cervical spine) for procedure will be given.

Under local anesthesia and with all aseptic precaution's procedure will be done. In a few cases like apprehensive patients, the procedure is performed with combination of local anesthesia and intravenous conscious sedation using benzodiazepine and analgesic. To reduce number of punctures all biopsies will be performed using coaxial needle.

Using appropriate coaxial stabilizing needle and appropriately sized aspiration or core biopsy needles specimens will be acquired from lesion. At the time of biopsy, images will be obtained in the area of interest and the needle tip must always be accounted for with respect to the target lesion and to all pertinent critical structures.

Specimens are smeared on glass slides and preserved in various types of containers, (normal saline container for mycobacterium, formalin container for cytology and gram stain) to be used for culture and histopathological specimens. All these specimens should be carefully labeled and dispatched. Specimens will be examined by pathologist and/or microbiologist and analysis of the lesion will be done.

During the procedure, we use low dose axial scan with 64 slice (Brilliance, Philips) or 128 slice (Ingenuity, Philips) MDCT scanner with Voltage-120 kvp, 30mAs per slice, Collimation of 5mm, Rotation time 0.5-1 sec.

Patient will be observed for 2-6 hours after the procedure with monitoring of vitals like pulse and blood pressure, oxygen saturation. Post procedure necessary antibiotics and analgesics are advised for 3-5 days. Operated case will be evaluated by pathologist & microbiologist. All the collected data will be analyzed by using proper bio-statistical methods.

Results

Diagnosis based on CT, Biopsy and final diagnosis based on radiological and repeat biopsy findings.

	CT	Biopsy (first biopsy)	Final (Following repeat biopsy)
Benign (n)	19	21	22
Malignant (n)	14	13	14
Tuberculosis (n)	11	5	7
Pyogenous (n)	01	2	2
Inconclusive (n)		4	

Sensitivity and specificity of CT and Biopsy:

Shows sensitivity and specificity of CT and initial biopsy in diagnosing malignancy and tuberculosis. CT had sensitivity of 85.71% and specificity of 93.54% for the diagnosis of malignancy and sensitivity of 85.71% and specificity of 86.48% for the diagnosis of tuberculosis. In contrast, initial biopsy

had sensitivity of 92.85% and specificity of 100% for the diagnosis of malignancy and sensitivity of 71.42% and specificity of 100% for the diagnosis of infection.

Sensitivity and specificity of CT findings and initial biopsy report to diagnose malignancy as well as infections in relationship to final diagnosis.

	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	Positive predictive value (%)	Negative predictive value (%)
Diagnosis of Malignancy based on CT findings	85.71	93.54	85.71	93.54
Diagnosis of tuberculosis based on CT findings	85.71	86.48	54.54	96.96
Diagnosis of Malignancy based on initial biopsy	92.85	100	100	96.87
Diagnosis of Infections based on initial biopsy.	71.42	100	100	95

CT findings and their correlation with final diagnosis.

CT features	Benign (n)	Malignant (n)	Infection (n)	Total
Posterior bulge with pathological fracture	15	4	0	19
Posterior bulge without pathological fracture	0	5	2	7
Involvement of posterior elements/pedicles	1	12	2	15
Epidural/paravertebral abscess	1	1	9	11
Soft tissue extension	2	6	0	8
Paradiscal involvement	2	0	8	10
Central involvement	21	13	1	35
Multiple levels	8	7	2	17

Positive microbiologic cultures were obtained in 148 cases

Dates	Biopsies performed	Organisms identified	Culture yield
January 2020–June 2020	34	10	29%
June 2020–January 2021	39	43	91%
January 2021–June 2021	20	64	36%

Dates	Biopsies performed	Organisms identified	Culture yield
June 2021–January 2022	16	84	19%
January 2022 – June 2022	30	87	32%
July 2022– December 2022	9	25	36%

This study had a culture yield rate of 91% (n = 39/43; 43 of 105 biopsies were performed in cases of suspected vertebral osteomyelitis), well above the pooled results mean of 37%. However, the authors note the strict inclusion criteria of their selected population “are not necessarily the criteria that one might use in a clinical setting” [15].

The most common pathogen isolated was Staphylococcus aureus (n = 40 34%). Other common pathogens included coagulase-negative Staphylococci (n = 23, 18%) and Mycobacteria (n = 18 16%; Mycobacteria tuberculosis n = 37). Fourteen of 105 organisms (6%)

Microbiological culture results	
Staphylococcus aureus	40
Coagulase-negative Staphylococci	23
Streptococcus pneumoniae	1
Streptococcus viridans	1
Streptococcus mitis	2
Group G Streptococci	1
Streptococcus anginosus	2
Streptococcus sanguinis	1

Other Streptococcus sp	2
Enterococcus sp	2
Cornybacterium sp	2
Propionibacterium acnes	4
Bifidobacterium	1
Clostridium bifermentas	1
Lactobacillus	1
Escherichia coli	4
Enterobacteriaceae	2
Pseudomonas sp	2
Klebsiella sp	1
Enterobacter cloacae	2
Proteus mirabilis	2
Acinetobacter lwoffii	1
Aggregatibacter aphrophilus	1
Citrobacter koseri	1
Bacteroides sp	3
Mycobacterium tuberculosis	15
Mycobacterium avium intracellulare	1
Candida sp	3
Others	

Discussion

In the modern era of evidence-based medicine, accuracy of diagnosis is very important, as it may lead to unnecessary treatment. Alison S. Smith et al., in their series found that MR findings of tubercular infection were more typical of neoplasm and feel clinical correlation is essential [8,17]. Need to establish diagnosis by biopsy was highlighted by other authors too before starting anti tubercular treatment [6,8,18]. Limitations in differentiating between malignant pathological fractures and osteoporotic fractures were highlighted by Tan SB et al., G Pozzi et al., [3,9]. G Pozzi et al., recommend DWI-MR imaging, although sclerotic metastases can be confusing and appear hypo intense [3,9]. Our study also supports this theory, we found that there was a change in diagnosis in 8 patients out of 45(17%), which is a significant number. We found that 2 cases were wrongly started on anti-tubercular treatment based on empirical treatment before presenting to us. While this could lead to unnecessary intake of tubercular drugs, may encourage drug resistant tuberculosis, it may also lead to progress of malignant lesion, which could make a big difference in converting a resectable lesion to non resectable lesion. One of the 2 cases was on empirical treatment (before presenting to us), had developed paraplegia and biopsy showed evidence of metastatic lesion; a timely biopsy and diagnosis could have prevented paraplegia. In suspected malignancy, biopsy is essential to establish tissue diagnosis and confirmation. Based on our observations we strongly recommend biopsy in all patients. Biopsy has high specificity, for diagnosis of both malignancy and infection, while has less sensitivity for the diagnosis of infection compared to MRI. Low sensitivity for tuberculosis was because of negative biopsy in 2 cases, which later

turned out to be tuberculosis with repeat biopsy.

These findings were consistent with other authors too, Rivas A et al., [19], found that biopsy has sensitivity of 86% and specificity of 100%. In view of high specificity, biopsy reports are reliable in initiating treatment. Although Gene Xpert MTB/RIF assay was not part of this study, with the emergence of drug resistant tuberculosis, there are strong recommendations for doing this assay on all samples in future, but, since ours was a retrospective study, we cannot address this issue. One of the concerns for biopsy is its being an invasive procedure.

However, biopsy can be performed with the help of an image or CT percutaneously. WCG Peh, opine that CT guided percutaneous biopsy is a safe and an affective technique for the evaluation of spinal lesions and useful in planning therapy [20]. While CT guided fine needle aspiration is simplest of all, the obtained sample tissue may not be adequate [12], image guided biopsy using a 11 gauge needle is also simple, can be performed with local anaesthesia and percutaneously. Large bore needle biopsy can be done under CT guidance also, but we feel biopsy in the operating room environment can be safer for a patient. Image guided biopsy is comparable with CT guided biopsy [21]. Our study focuses on effectiveness of a needle biopsy using Jamshedi needle, as this procedure can be done under local anaesthesia under image guidance and can get enough material for making a diagnosis thus avoiding complications of open biopsy.

Our findings indicate that the diagnostic culture yield for CT-guided biopsies in cases of suspected spinal infection is 33%. This is lower than the diagnostic culture yield of blood cultures in monomicrobial patterns of pyogenic spondylodiscitis, which is

approximately 59% [8,17] and ranges from 20%–78% [6], [18]. However, this could be confounded by the IDSA guidelines. In cases where a microbiologic diagnosis for a known associated organism has been obtained (including *S. aureus*, *Brucella* sp.), CT-guided vertebral biopsies are not recommended [9].

In spinal infection, diagnostic culture yield is known to be higher in open biopsies than percutaneous biopsies. It remains unclear why the diagnostic yield is so low in comparison to other specimen acquisition methods. However, the pathophysiology of vertebral osteomyelitis and spondylodiscitis may play a role. In adults, hematogenous spread of infection typically seeds the subchondral bone of the vertebral bodies first, before spreading locally into the intervertebral discs. It is generally recommended that tissue samples include subchondral bone; paravertebral abscesses and intervertebral fluid are usually sterile [8,4]. Of the studies included in the analysis, 2 [16], [20] evaluated only bone specimens, 2 included disc or abscess fluid but not bone, whereas the remaining studies either included a combination of the 3 sample sources [4] or failed to report that information [13]. Given the lack of information regarding distribution of sample source, it is possible that paravertebral collections were preferentially sampled and nondiagnostic biopsies were performed. Interestingly, Chang et al compared the yield for paravertebral soft-tissue versus endplate versus disc and found no statistically significant difference [24]. Heyer et al suggested that chronic inflammation within a vertebral body leads to increased sclerosis and decreased blood supply, which could contribute to poor diagnostic yields even in osseous samples of infected vertebral bodies [16]. Others have postulated that the amount of sclerosis is dependent on the infection itself and is affected by the duration of infection as well as the microorganism type [26]. Both Spira et al and Foreman et al reported increased yield in the presence of increased inflammation [14], [23]. Perhaps image-guided sampling technique also plays a role in diagnostic yield. Using percutaneous endoscopic discectomy and drainage, Yang et al observed significantly better diagnostic yield compared to CT-guided biopsy (18/20 [90%] versus 15/20 [47%] respectively, $P = 0.002$) [13]. The accuracy of this technique has been attributed to the relatively larger volume of sample attained. However, if enhanced yield were related to volume alone, one would expect to observe a consistent pattern with regard to the gauge of sampling needle used in CT-guided aspiration. On the contrary, no such relationship was observed in any of the studies included in the review that specifically analyzed this variable (Chang et al found a non-statistically significant trend toward lower yield with smaller Gauge) [24]. The most common causative organism in our review was *Staphylococcus* ($n = 83$ *Staphylococcus aureus*, $n = 45$ coagulase negative *Staphylococci*) followed

by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* ($n = 37$). This correlates with the literature, which lists *S. aureus* and *E. coli* as the most common pathogens [1]. Only 5 of the studies specifically mentioned that samples were sent for M.

tuberculosis culture [13], [15], [21], [22], [24]. Two studies reported positive *M. tuberculosis* in their results without adequate description of their microbiological investigation methods [23], [25]. Michel et al noted the addition of Ziehl-Nielsen staining on only 11 of their 41 specimens [4] and Heyer et al used histology for the diagnosis of *M. tuberculosis* [16]. Foreman et al described their microbiology methods in detail but omitted *Mycobacterial* testing [14].

Anaerobic organisms have increasingly been implicated in cases of spinal infection [1]. This correlates with our findings; 6% of isolated organisms were anaerobic bacteria. *Propionibacterium acnes*, a Gram-positive anaerobe, was listed among the most common causative organisms detected. *P. acnes* is often considered a skin contaminant; Chang et al included 2 samples that grew it in their list of false positive results [24]. However, some speculate that this bacterium plays a role in the development of Modic Type 1 and Type 2 changes in degenerative disc disease [27]. Therefore, it is imperative that both aerobic and anaerobic cultures, in addition to microbiological analysis, fungal cultures, and mycobacteria cultures Acid-Fast Bacilli (AFB) smear, and are performed to optimize diagnostic culture yield. One periprocedural metric that produced statistically significant culture results was antibiotic administration before biopsy. Marco de Lucas et al identified causative organisms in 60% of cases without previous antibiotics, and only 23% of cases that had been treated with antibiotics within 48 hours before the procedure ($P = 0.027$) [21]. Marco de Lucas et al targeted only intravertebral disc or abscess fluid, often obtaining <3 mL of fluid for culture. Chang et al, Heyer et al, and Garg et al performed a similar comparison, evaluating the effect of pre-biopsy antimicrobials on yield, and found no statistically significant difference. Both Heyer et al and Garg et al sampled a combination of vertebral bone, disc, and abscess fluid. Garg et al specifically noted collecting >20 mL of fluid if abscess material alone was obtained. Perhaps the observed difference described by Marco de Lucas et al was confounded by inadequate sample volume. Analyses looking specifically at the impact of antimicrobials on bone biopsy culture yield have similarly found no association [19], [28], [29].

Among the individual studies, no technical metric during or after the biopsy procedure was found to have a statistically significant effect on culture results within their internal populations [4], [13]. Of particular interest in our review was the specimen transfer method. Unfortunately, only 4 studies

described their method in requisite detail. Marco de Lucas et al had a cytopathologist present in the interventional radiology suite. Tissue samples were placed on glass slides immediately and were examined by the cytopathologist to determine specimen adequacy. The culture yield for Marco de Lucas et al was 23% [21], below the pooled results mean of 33%. Rieneck et al cultivated their biopsy material in the interventional radiology suite immediately next to the patient [20]. This resulted in an above average diagnostic culture yield of 57%. Foreman et al immediately transferred specimens in sterile saline to microbiology for homogenization and plating. Their culture yield was 40%, also above the mean [14]. Similarly, Chang et al placed their specimens in nonbacteriostatic saline solution in sterile vials and transported them to microbiology in less than 4 hours. This resulted in a 36% culture yield [24]. Only 3 studies clearly described the protocols used for culture and identification (Chang et al, Foreman et al, and Rieneck et al) [14], [20], [24]. No study employed molecular diagnostic techniques for bacterial or fungal identification.

The majority of articles did not comment on whether repeat biopsies were performed. However, Marco de Lucas et al reported that 4 patients underwent 2 biopsies with technically adequate but negative initial biopsies [21]. Of these patients, all had been administered empiric antibiotics in the interval. Three had a negative second biopsy, and the fourth was positive for *M. tuberculosis* for which the patient had not been adequately empirically treated. An additional patient underwent 3 biopsies after 2 initial negative results. The third biopsy was positive for *S. aureus* [21]. This suggests that repeat biopsies may be useful in clinically challenging cases. The statistical analysis revealed a negative correlation between year of study publication and diagnostic culture yield. This could be related to the increased use of CT-guided percutaneous spinal biopsies over the years. With improved availability, CT-guided biopsies are used in a growing number of technically difficult and clinically occult cases. Further, the results were skewed by the 1996 study from Chew et al, which, as discussed previously, had a 91% diagnostic yield but only included patients with confirmed infections via microbiological analysis [15]. A major limitation of this review stems from the heterogeneity of metrics in the 11 studies. Unfortunately, it was difficult to evaluate if any particular variable, such as biopsy method or specimen transfer and processing method, had a statistically significant effect on diagnostic culture yield across multiple papers. Another major limitation was that nearly all included studies were retrospective reviews. Michel et al was not explicitly described as retrospective [4]. Lastly, as there exists an imperfect Gold standard for the diagnosis of vertebral osteomyelitis, there was considerable heterogeneity in how each study defined their reference method. Some studies

employed a composite reference including microbiological diagnosis or histopathology, radiological appearance, and clinical response to antimicrobial therapy; whereas others utilized positive microbiology or histopathology alone or heavily relied on clinician judgment. This not only makes comparison between studies difficult but also makes any measure of clinical sensitivity, specificity, or accuracy difficult to determine.

Conclusions:

Image guided Biopsy done with a good technique helps in achieving accurate diagnosis, ensures correct treatment at the earliest and has minimal complications. In conclusion, the diagnostic culture yield for CT-guided biopsies in cases of suspected spinal infection is low, approximately 33%. The reasons for this are likely multifactorial and have of yet not been clearly defined, including the effect of pre-administration of antibiotics [21], biopsy technique, inadequate sample volume, suboptimal specimen transfer methods, and culture techniques. Further study of these individual variables is required with a clearly defined and universally applied standard reference method.

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